

Demystifying how emotional and cognitive resonance to AI-driven content consistency sparks customer engagement and impulse buying in short-video E-commerce

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ABSTRACT

This study is the first to integrate the association of three dimensions of AI-based content recommendation's consistency (information, image and presence) and customer engagement including learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy and co-developing in short-video platforms. Drawing on Cue Consistency Theory, Resonance Theory, and SOR model, the study investigates how these consistency factors influence customer engagement and impulse buying through emotional and cognitive resonance, with the focus on the moderating roles of perceived serendipity and platform stickiness. A total of 679 responses were collected in Vietnam, and the data were analyzed using PLS-SEM. The results reveal that presence consistency positively influences emotional resonance, while information and image consistency positively impact cognitive resonance. Moreover, cognitive resonance is positively associated with impulse buying, and platform stickiness moderates the relationship between emotional resonance and customer engagement. Theoretically, this study extends cue consistency theory to AI-based recommendation contexts by incorporating emotional and cognitive resonance into a unified model. Managerially, the findings offer actionable insights for platform developers, marketers, content creators, and e-commerce sellers to fine-tune recommendation algorithm, improve their content strategies and ultimately foster stronger user experience and enhance conversion rate in an increasingly competitive digital market.

1. Introduction

In recent years, Artificial intelligence (AI) has been applied in various domains such as healthcare (Kalra et al., 2024; Reddy, 2024), banking (Emmanuel et al., 2024; AI-Dosari et al., 2024), transportation (Pérez-Cerrolaza et al., 2023; Kuo and Choi, 2024) and management (Chowdhury et al., 2024; Pallathadka et al., 2023). However, one of the most outstanding applications of AI is in the recommender system, where the system collects data from to determine their preferences and then suggest appropriate content (Deldjoo Yashar et al., 2023), which now drives 80 % of viewing time on Netflix and accounts for 35 % Amazon's total sales (Welcon, 2024; Market.us, 2024). On short video platforms such as TikTok, 61 % of users discover new brands and 92 % take action after watching AI-recommended content (The Social Shepherd, 2025). These platforms have been increasingly prevalent globally (Liu et al., 2021), reflecting both the demand of fast-paced lifestyle and the appeal of condensed, engaging content (Wright, 2017). Because of

this nature, AI-based content recommendation plays a key role in improving customer experience, particularly by helping users filter through overwhelming volumes of content (Xiang et al., 2024). Moreover, such recommendations can also influence our beliefs, decisions and actions (Deldjoo Yashar et al., 2023). Thus, it is crucial to explore how AI-based content recommendation impacts users both cognitively and emotionally and finally their behaviors.

This study focuses on four key constructs: consistency in AI-based content recommendations, emotional and cognitive resonance, customer engagement, and impulse buying. In this study, AI-based content recommendation is characterized by its consistency in information, image and presence of each video delivered to the audience in short video platforms. Although these concepts have only recently been applied in digital media research (Kaur and Kaur, 2021; Rao and Dixit, 2025), their importance is underscored by studies such as Hsieh (2023), which found that consistent cues from influencers significantly affect how followers identify with them cognitively and affectively. Along with

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consistency, resonance is another central concept, referring to both cognitive and emotional connections that users experience in response to AI-recommended content. In previous scholars, resonance was found to have a positive influence on destination image, travel intention and WOM intention (Chen et al., 2025; Cheng et al., 2020; Mohanty et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023, 2024). In fast-paced short-video environments, where attention spans are short and emotional triggers are frequent, this connection plays a crucial role in determining whether content is merely viewer or meaningfully engaged with.

Despite growing interest in AI-powered platforms, several gaps remain in the current literature. Most existing studies on short-video platforms tend to focus on user addiction or social influences (Fei et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2022), while the commercial value and content features driving engagements are underexplored (Xiao et al., 2023). Moreover, research on recommendation systems has primarily addressed technical aspects or negative effects (Chen et al., 2021; Li, 2023; Zhao, 2021), overlooking key psychological drivers like entertainment, inspiration, escapism and cognitive factors such as information acquisition, source credibility, and knowledge externalization. This orientation has led to an oversight of psychological factors that may play a key role in shaping user experience with AI-recommended content. Another notable gap concerns the concept of consistency in AI-based content recommendation. There has been no research delving into the consistency aspect of AI-based content recommendation as prior studies often focus on experience which users have with the recommendation in such platforms such as trendiness, aesthetic value, information quantity, personalization quality, entertainment, and accuracy (Nguyen et al., 2024) or different dimensions such as accuracy, interactivity, and personalization of the AI recommendation system (Zhang, 2025). In terms of customer engagement, most past studies generally examined it through cognitive, affection, and behaviors (Rather, 2019; Lin et al., 2024; Yoo, 2024) or based on metrics of likes, shares, and comments (Schivinski et al., 2016; Cheng et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2023), neglecting the deeper, multidimensions of engagement levels. While the SOR model remains dominant in studies on recommendation systems, the reliance on this single framework leaves a notable gap in the application of alternative theories that could offer fresh perspectives. For instance, SOR theory was adopted to examine how personalized tourism recommendations (PTR) shape visit intentions through technology trust and PTR attitude (Yang et al., 2023) or explain how recommendation accuracy, streamer attractiveness, and C2C interactions on TikTok streaming commerce influence purchase intentions, with function and social values and immersion as organismic states (Wang et al., 2024,b). Although these studies demonstrate the flexibility of SOR, they highlight the need for alternative frameworks to better explain cognitive and emotional mechanism in digital contexts.

Many existing studies on social media have explored different drivers of online impulse buying (Koay and Lim, 2024; Safer, 2024). Although these works provide valuable insights, most focus on emotional factors with limited attention to cognitive dimensions. In the realm of cognition, prior research has largely examined cognitive dissonance as a consequence of impulse buying, rather than as a potential antecedent (Lin et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021). Research in the context of short video platforms remains scarce, particularly the role of cognitive resonance, or the alignment between users' cognitive beliefs and brand or product messages in driving impulse buying has been largely overlooked (Huang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024).

Emotional resonance and cognitive resonance are also critical variables that need a deeper investigation. In this study, we aim to examine whether consistency in information, image, and presence can stimulate an audience's cognitive state, and whether this level of cognition subsequently drives behavioral responses. Previously, these two concepts were mainly applied in tourism domain to learn how cognitive resonance and emotional resonance influence conative destination image (Wang et al., 2023) - their role in short video platforms remains underexplored.

Thus, this study aims to provide a deeper understanding of how AI-based content recommendation operates on short-video platforms by focusing on the consistency of recommended videos. Specifically, it is the first study to examine AI-based content recommendation through three dimensions of consistency - information, image and presence. Building on this, the research investigates how such consistency generates cognitive and emotional resonance, and in turn how these resonance responses shape users' behavioral outcomes, including engagement and impulse buying. To address the theoretical gaps identified, this study adopts a multi-theoretical approach, including the SOR model, cue consistency theory and resonance theory, offering a comprehensive understanding of how consistency functions as a stimulus that triggers both cognitive and affective processing in users. Furthermore customer engagement is conceptualized as a multi-dimensional variable, comprising learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy, and co-developing - going beyond traditional behavioral metrics to capture deeper levels of user involvement. In addition to theoretical values, the findings offer actionable insights for platform developers, policy makers, brands, and influencers on maintaining content and presence consistency to build stronger resonance and trust, while balancing novelty and familiarity. By applying these insights, stakeholders can improve recommendation quality, strengthen user relationships, and more effectively stimulate their engagement and buying behaviors.

1.1. Theoretical background

1.1.1. SOR model

The Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) framework was first introduced for academic purposes by Mehrabian and Russell in 1974 to explain how external stimuli influence individuals' internal states and behaviors. The model includes three key attributes: stimuli, organism, and response, which collectively shape consumers' attitudes (Wang et al., 2018). Stimuli refers to external factors that trigger human emotional and cognitive responses (Eroglu et al., 2001). In previous studies, various external cues have been used as stimuli within the SOR model. Baber and Baber (2022) investigated social media marketing efforts as a stimulus that affect tourists' intention to visit, while Zhou and Ma (2025) examines how the stimulus - generative AI content quality and generative AI system quality impact users' continuance intention. In this study, AI-based content recommendation (information consistency, presence consistency and image consistency) was operationalized as the stimulus in the SOR framework. The organism represents humans' cognitive and affective states, such as how they perceive, experience, and feel about something (Bagozzi, 1986). In the context of this study, organisms are emotional resonance (congruence, inspiration, entertainment, escapism) and cognitive resonance (information acquisition, source credibility, knowledge externalization) provoked by AI-generated content. Finally, response is the observable behavior shaped by environmental stimuli and internal states (Mehrabian and Russell, 1974). In this research, impulse buying and customer engagement (learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy, co-developing) are conceptualized as responses toward AI-based content recommendation in short-video platforms.

1.1.2. Cue consistency theory

Cue consistency theory posits that people form more favourable evaluations when multiple informational cues about a subject are congruent (Maheswaran and Chaiken, 1991; Slovic, 1966). Building on this theory, prior research has examined the impact of consistent cues on shaping people's attitude and behaviors. For instance, Miyazaki et al. (2005) studied how consistent product-related cues influence perceived product quality, while Hsieh (2023) explored how influencers' cue consistency affects the social identification of their followers on social networking sites. As emphasized by Anderson (1981) and Maheswaran and Chaiken (1991), the impact of these cues is greater when multiple

sources provide corroborating, rather than conflicting messages. In case two cues are inconsistent, the influence of the stronger or more positive cue is diminished, and people's evaluation resembles those formed under entirely weak or negative cues. In this way, consistent cues are averaged with equal weight, while inconsistent cues are given unequal weight, with more inclination to negative ones (Miyazaki et al., 2005). The cue consistency theory suggests that multiple informational cues can be combined to influence people's perceptions and decisions (Maheswaran and Chaiken, 1991). Applied to this study, when AI-based content recommendation maintains consistency across information, presence and image, it can foster stronger emotional and cognitive engagement among users.

1.1.3. Resonance theory

The concept of resonance was initially introduced in organization studies to explain the superiority of certain framings compared to others (Benford and Snow, 2000; Snow and Benford, 1988; Snow et al., 1986). Researchers have applied it to examine the alignment between a message and the audience's perspective (McDonnell et al., 2017). There are two types of resonance: cognitive resonance, which appeals to audiences' cognition and emotional resonance, appealing to their emotions (Giorgi, 2017). Specifically, cognition refers to how people think, plan, and solve a problem (Jepperson et al., 1991), while emotions encompass feeling, passions, and desires that can not be fully explained by logical reasoning or the pursuit of self-interest (Voronov and Vince, 2012). Cognitive resonance occurs when framing aligns with an audience's understanding, values or beliefs (Giorgi, 2017), meanwhile emotional resonance arises when people's curiosity and desire are triggered (Kang et al., 2020). This theory was applied to investigate how effective resonance influences word-of-mouth and travel behavioral these cases, high-quality online information increases tourists' resonance, ultimately influencing their perceptions of destination conative image (Cheng et al., 2020; Mohanty et al., 2022). In this research, the theory of resonance will be applied to explore the impact of consistency in AI-generated content in short video platforms on people's emotional and cognitive resonance, and consequently observable behaviors.

This study primarily builds upon the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model as its main theoretical foundation, supported by Cue consistency theory and Resonance theory. The SOR model provides an overarching framework to explain the process through which AI-based content recommendations (stimuli) influence users' internal states (organism) and subsequently shape their responses. Within this framework, cue consistency theory is incorporated to specify how alignment among environmental cues can enhance users' perceptions, thus strengthening the initial stimulus. This theoretical lens enriches the SOR model by clarifying why certain external signals are more likely to capture user's attention. Furthermore, resonance theory is also adopted to increase explanatory power of the proposed model by interpreting the way cognitive and emotional resonance are generated and then result in various outcomes. Integrating three theories enables the study to comprehensively explore the real-world complexity of AI-based content recommendation in short video platforms.

1.1.4. Customer engagement

Customer engagement is widely recognized as a key concept in marketing, attracting extensive scholarly attention on its definition, antecedents, and outcomes. Vivek et al. (2012) laid the theoretical foundations by positioning customer engagement as the "expanded domain of relationship marketing" drawing upon foundational insights from Morgan and Hunt's (1994), Vargo and Lusch (2004), Vargo and Lusch (2008), Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004). Meanwhile, Brodie et al. (2011) further developed the concept, defining 'customer engagement' as "a psychological state that occurs by virtue of interactive, co-creative customer experiences with a focal agent/object (e.g. a brand).

Customer engagement is regarded as essential for driving effective

social marketing outcomes (Bazi et al., 2023; Hollebeek et al., 2014; Roy et al., 2023). With the prevalence of AI technology, customer engagement has been significantly enhanced. As customers increasingly seek personalized interactions, AI-enabled experiences improve satisfaction, sustain engagement, shape purchasing decisions and encourage platform interaction (Okeke et al., 2024; Nguyen et al., 2024). In e-commerce, AI-based recommendations such as personalized marketing messages, product and promotion recommendations help create customized experiences, increasing sales and satisfaction (Zhang, 2024).

In this study, customer engagement is measured by five dimensions: learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy, co-developing, which are adopted from five specific consumer engagement sub-processes developed by Brodie et al. (2011). This multidimensional approach is adopted because it illustrates how engagement can progress in intensity. The sequence moves from one-way interaction such as learning, to reciprocal exchanges like sharing and socializing, and finally to co-creation.

Accordingly, this research conceptualizes and evaluates customer engagement based on the following five dimensions.

1.1.4.1. Learning. Learning has been recognized as a key component of consumer behavior in digital environments (Chiang et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2022; Behnam et al., 2021), which was defined as the indirect development of knowledge and cognitive skills assisting consumers in making informed decisions about purchasing products or services Brodie et al. (2013). In digital context, Heinonen (2018) observed that social media platforms enable self-expansion by facilitating access to new relationships, experiences, and learning opportunities. Similarly, Muntinga et al. (2011) identified knowledge acquisition - alongside seeking inspiration, gathering pre-purchase information, and staying informed - as one of the main motivations for user engagement with trending content on social media. Taken together, learning should be considered a relevant dimension in measuring customer engagement with AI-based content recommendations on short video platforms.

1.1.4.2. Sharing. Sharing has become a central element of how people experience media content (Hermida et al., 2012), involving the act of distribution, communication and consumption (Belk, 2010; John, 2012c). Brodie et al. (2013) define sharing as consumers actively contributing their personal experiences, insights, and relevant knowledge to collaboratively enrich the collective understanding within a community. This behavior is valuable not only because it provides audiences with shareable content (Jenkins et al., 2013), but also because it allows media organizations to reach new audiences and keep their existing customer pool connected (Himmelboim and McCreery, 2012). For example, Brodie et al. (2013) describe a user who, after using a WBV machine for seven months, felt confident to contribute to discussions and answer basic questions posed by newcomers. For this reason, sharing is an indispensable aspect to assess customer engagement with AI-based content recommendation in short video platforms.

1.1.4.3. Socializing. Socializing refers to reciprocal, non-instrumental interactions where consumers build shared norms, values, or a sense of belonging within a community (Longmore, 1998). In the context of online forums, Meek et al. (2018) found that people are motivated to participate not only for information but also for opportunities to socialize. This is also aligned with the finding of Zhou et al. (2013) when he stated that information and social relationships are perceived equally important to consumers. For instance, one respondent shared that because their online community had a small group of around 10 to 15 active members, they developed a sense of familiarity and closeness, describing it as "a feeling of knowing each other" (Brodie et al., 2013). Therefore, it is justifiable to include socializing as an instrument of customer engagement.

1.1.4.4. Advocacy. From the traditional view, advocacy has been

described as “the act of publicly representing an individual, organization, or idea with the object of persuading targeted audiences to look favorably on - or accept the point of view - the individual, the organization, the idea” (Edgett, 2002). In the context of social media platforms, advocacy is much more effective when individuals or groups can easily lure, involve and mobilize others in real time actions (Bresciani and Schmeil, 2012). Consumer advocacy represents a form of engagement in which individuals actively endorse particular brands, products, or usage methods. For example, a person who advocates the brand can leave a comment that “I think that the [brand name] is suitable for you. Very powerful and very underpriced” Brodie et al. (2013). Thus, the authors propose that advocacy should be among the aspects used to assess customer engagement towards AI-based content recommendation.

1.1.4.5. Co-developing. Co-developing was described as “a psychological state which occurs by virtue of interactive, co-creative customer experiences with a focal object within a dynamic, iterative process of service relationships that co-creates value” Brodie et al. (2011). As further elaborated by Brodie et al. (2013), co-developing describes consumers’ active participation in shaping or improving products, services, or brand meanings, thereby contributing to a firm’s value creation process. Another term that is similar to co-developing is co-creation, in which users “actively give feedback about their experience, questions and improvement suggestions for the intelligent customer service robots” (Vo et al., 2024). The same study further notes that “value co-creation is driven by customers’ positive engagement experience (e.g. engagement, attitudes, perceived usefulness) or technology attributes (e.g. social presence, personalization, interactivity)”. These studies underscore the importance of including co-developing as a dimension of customer engagement.

1.2. Hypotheses development

1.2.1. AI-based content recommendation and cognitive resonance

We examine AI-based content recommendation through a three-dimensional framework, including information consistency, image consistency and presence consistency (Hsieh, 2023). Hossain et al. (2019) defined information consistency as the extent to which a business spreads its information consistently across all its marketing channels. In our study, information consistency refers to the extent to which the system delivers coherent and thematically aligned information. Image consistency, as emphasized by Hossain et al. (2019) and extended by Hsieh (2023), denotes the consistent representation of visual and personality elements - such as names, characteristics, and aesthetic features - across platforms. In our study, image consistency refers to the degree to which the visual representation of similar content remains aesthetically and stylistically coherent across multiple short videos. Presence consistency, introduced in this study, refers to the stability and focus of content, brands, or creators recommended over time. Similar to review consistency, presence consistency acts as a heuristic cue that helps users process and evaluate content more efficiently Cheung et al. (2012).

Cognitive resonance stems from the audience’s beliefs and understanding (Giorgi, 2017). Cheng et al. (2020) defined cognitive resonance as the extent to which an object aligns with a viewer’s values, beliefs and interpretation. In this study, cognitive resonance comprises three elements: information acquisition, source credibility and knowledge externalization. Berger (2014), for example, highlighted information acquisition in the context of travel vlogs, defining it as a key factor contributing to cognitive resonance by satisfying their curiosity and gaining useful knowledge. Likewise, Park et al. (2009) suggested that when users perceive content as valuable, such as a Facebook post, then they are more likely to share it to other people. Source credibility refers to the perceived trustworthiness and expertise of the information provider, such as an endorser or influencer (Berlo et al., 1969; Bhattacharjee and Sanford, 2006; Zha et al., 2017). Finally, externalization is the

process of articulating and sharing internal ideas or tacit knowledge during innovation phases, which helps users internalize and communicate new knowledge effectively (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). This process often occurs in formal interactions, such as discussions between consumers and technology experts (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995; Crawford and Benedetto, 2015). Although no previous studies have directly demonstrated the relationship between knowledge externalization and cognitive resonance, the interactions through comments, shares, or discussions give consumers a sense of immersion and satisfaction, which in turn lead to cognitive resonance (Hu et al., 2023).

Studies showed that consistent cues in information have a positive impact on user’s cognitive resonance. A study of (Hsieh, 2023) on social networking sites suggested that the more consistent information is, the higher level of cognitive and affective identification between followers is. For example, a follower can shape a positive cognitive evaluation towards an influencer when this person conveys consistent messages. This study also aligns with cue consistency theory, which highlights the importance of consistent signals influencing audience perception and reaction. When people encounter consistent cues from their environment, they incorporate these signals into their thought process, influencing their psychological states (De Roeck and Farooq, 2018). In contrast, inconsistency in informational cues across channels can erode trust and cause cognitive dissonance, frustrating users and reducing their engagement (Hsieh et al., 2012; Rangaswamy and Van Bruggen, 2005; Festinger, 1957). In the context of our study, the consistency given by AI-based content recommendation can generate cognitive resonance by aiding information acquisition, enhancing source credibility and facilitating knowledge externalization. Under the customer review context, information consistency can significantly reduce information overload (Kim et al., 2017), whereas inconsistency tends to induce ambivalence and discomfort for message receivers (Chang, 2016; Monteith, 1996). When informational cues are strongly aligned, the process of information acquisition is facilitated, thereby enhancing cognitive resonance. Regarding presence consistency, discrepancies in online presentation can negatively affect perceptions of a person’s credibility and likability (Tang et al., 2020). Similarly, DeAndrea and Walther (2011) found that deviations between online and offline presentations reduce perceived trustworthiness. Hence, maintaining presence consistency can strengthen source credibility and help foster cognitive resonance. In terms of image consistency, when a celebrity’s image aligns with that of the endorsed brand, the brand image is strengthened and audiences perceive the brand more favorably (Schimmelpfennig and Hunt, 2020).

With the above discussion relating to AI-Based content recommendation and its three dimensions along with its influences toward cognitive resonance, we hypothesize as follow.

H1a. Information consistency is positively associated with cognitive resonance.

H1b. Presence consistency is positively associated with cognitive resonance.

H1c. Image consistency is positively associated with cognitive resonance.

1.2.2. AI-based content recommendation and emotional resonance

While cognitive resonance originates from the way people perceive and comprehend, emotional resonance is related to the way people feel, have passion or desire about something (Giorgi, 2017). Emotional resonance arises from people’s emotional attachment to content, which can trigger psychological responses like anger, happiness, or fear, etc (Stroud, 2010; The Filter Bubble, 2025). Kang et al. (2020) further suggested that curiosity and desire can also lead to emotional resonance. In this study, emotional resonance is examined through four dimensions, including congruence, entertainment, inspiration and escapism. Congruence refers to the fit between an individual’s self-concept and a

product user's image (Sirgy and Su, 2000). In our context, congruence is how users perceive the match between AI-based content recommendation and people's values and experiences. Entertainment is the second factor constituting emotional resonance, which is identified as the mental state of individuals who actively engage with entertaining content, whether related to products or people (Berger, 2014). Next, inspiration is defined as a formation of beliefs influenced by encounters with what is true, good, or beautiful (Elliot and Church, 1997; Thrash and Elliot, 2003; Kim and Fesenmaier, 2008). Finally, escapism means a psychological retreat from stress or boredom, where individuals become deeply immersed in an activity (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990; Hosany and Witham, 2010).

Emotional resonance in this study is proposed to be triggered by consistent cues from AI-based content recommendation. When information is delivered consistently across various platforms, it can foster positive emotional responses (Lazaris et al., 2022). For example, Fiez et al. (1999) found that consistency between visual and auditory elements improves emotional processing. Similarly, alignment between salesperson and the brand can lead to stronger positive emotional responses from consumers (Lee and Yi, 2018). Conversely, inconsistency in brand presentation may provoke negative affective reactions (Landers et al., 2015). In the case of AI-based content recommendation, consistency in tone, theme and identity across suggested content contributes to a more harmonious and emotionally engaging experience. Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H2a. Information consistency is positively associated with emotional resonance.

H2b. Presence consistency is positively associated with emotional resonance.

H2c. Image consistency is positively associated with emotional resonance.

1.2.3. Cognitive resonance and impulse buying

Impulse buying refers to an unplanned purchase, typically sudden, emotionally driven and difficult to control (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998; Rook, 1987). This behavior typically involves minimal deliberation, limited evaluation of alternatives, and a focus on immediate gratification rather than thoughtful decision-making. It is commonly triggered by what (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998) describe as an impulse buying urge - a spontaneous desire that arises upon encountering a product in a particular environment. Previous studies have focused on finding antecedents of impulse buying such as emotional and cognitive state, normative evaluation, sales, promotion, etc (Dawson and Kim, 2009). Recently, impulse buying has risen remarkably due to the advancement of information technology and the explosion of e-commerce (Kathuria and Bakshi, 2024).

In this study, cognitive resonance comprises source credibility, information acquisition, and knowledge externalization - each of which contributes to impulse buying behavior. Source credibility plays a crucial role in shaping consumer decisions, particularly in the online environment. For example, Rajat et al. (2024) emphasized website credibility as an impactful cognitive element in online shopping, as customers are visually appealed and become motivated to make purchases. Regarding information acquisition, it often occurs unexpectedly - similar to information encountering, such as when users browse short video platforms and come across content via recommendation systems rather than deliberately search (Sun and Adnan, 2025). When the encountered information is adequate and useful, it enables consumers to obtain valuable knowledge (Cheng et al., 2020), which further reinforces their confidence in the content. Kim et al. (2018) found that source credibility is a crucial factor which affects consumers' decision-making, attitudes, and intentions to purchase. Finally, knowledge externalization shapes impulse buying by facilitating collective meaning-making through interaction. In the context of AI-based content

recommendation, users do not passively absorb information but actively interpret it, share, discuss and reshape it through exchanges with others. This process is nearly similar to consumer socialization in which consumers obtain skills, knowledge and attitudes from others through communication (Ward, 1974), however it is more formal as it involves the participation of experts to understand the value of the content, form new insights and gain clarity. Consumer socialization can lead to various outcomes such as brand preference, involvement, or purchase intention (Wang et al., 2012), which mean knowledge externalization may result in buying behavior or even impulse buying. Therefore, we suggest.

H3a. Cognitive resonance is positively associated with Impulse buying.

1.2.4. Emotional resonance and impulse buying

Emotional resonance characterized by congruence, entertainment, inspiration, and escapism has an essential role in shaping consumers' impulse buying behavior. These emotional responses foster psychological alignment between consumer and environmental stimulus, resulting in spontaneous purchases more likely. Among these components, congruence plays a foundational role. Japutra et al. (2019) linked self-congruence to impulse buying, emphasizing its pivotal role in fostering identification with a product, which encourages unplanned purchases. Supporting this, Edwards (1996) and Darrat et al. (2016) found that enthusiasm, emotional stability and congruence can lead to impulse purchase. Koay and Lim (2024) further explained that self-congruence helps consumers feel aligned with their values and experiences, motivating them to engage in online impulse purchases. While congruence fosters identification, emotional resonance is also enhanced through entertainment. Yu and Bastin (2010) noted that enjoyable and humorous experiences can trigger impulse buying. Similarly, Yi et al. (2020) emphasized that entertainment value creates positive emotional response and fulfills psychological needs, which in turn encourage impulse online purchase. Beyond enjoyment, inspiration adds a motivational layer to emotional resonance. Böttger et al. (2017) defined customer inspiration as a temporary motivational state that facilitates the transition from receiving a marketing-induced idea to the pursuit of a consumption goal, and serves as a psychological bridge between external stimuli and spontaneous purchase actions. Böttger et al. (2017) also found that product description containing a high level of inspirational content often evokes consumer's impulse to purchase. Finally, escapism contributes to emotional resonance by offering consumers a way to mentally detach from daily stressors (Korgaonkar and Wolin, 1999). described escapism as a key motive for online shopping, especially when individuals seek distraction or emotional relief. The hedonic value of shopping, rooted in feelings of novelty, enjoyment, and the sense of escape amplifies emotional engagement and encourages impulse buying (DSpace, 2025). Thus, we propose.

H3b. Emotional resonance is positively associated with Impulse buying.

1.2.5. Cognitive resonance and customer engagement

Cognitive resonance is essential in boosting customer engagement because it reinforces the match between customer's existing perception and the information they encounter. Specifically, individuals have a tendency to perceive content as trustworthy and relevant once they see similarity (homophily) or information usefulness from the marketing communications or user-generated content (Schouten et al., 2019). This perceived alignment increases the credibility of the communicator and reduces skepticism, especially in contexts such as tourism short videos, where cognitive resonance leads consumers to interpret the content as authentic recommendations rather than promotional messaging (Zha et al., 2017). As a result, users are more likely to engage through actions like commenting, sharing, or expressing intentions to visit (Cheng et al., 2020). Moreover, cognitive resonance increases perceived personal involvement, which in turn predicts continued viewing intentions and

behavioral outcomes, including decision-making and online engagement (Yu, 2021). Importantly, when cognitive resonance is combined with emotional resonance, it fosters deeper cognitive processing and strengthens users' identification with content, thereby encouraging active participation in digital environments Yang et al. (2025). Thus, we propose.

H4a. Cognitive resonance is positively associated with Customer engagement.

1.2.6. Emotional resonance and customer engagement

Based on (Torkzadeh et al., 2022), customer engagement includes both psychological and behavioral activities consumers undertake during their interactions with a company. Customer engagement goes beyond buying behaviors, it can come in various types of customer interaction (Gandhi et al., 2023; Hollebeek et al., 2014). Zhang and Wang (2025) defined the relationships between customer resonances (cognitive and emotional) and customer engagement (psychology and behavior). Cheng, Wei, and Zhang (2020) also examined how surfing tourism information can affect their emotional resonance, which sequentially lead to intention to travel to suggested places. Zhang and Wang (2025) learnt the influences of emotional resonance on customer engagement in the specific context of short videos about traveling. It is found that when users interact with content creators and information in traveling short videos, they create emotional resonance which in turns transform into both psychological engagement (acceptance and immersion), as well as behavioral engagement (recommendations and purchases). Consequently, we hypothesize.

H4b. Emotional resonance is positively associated with Customer engagement.

1.2.7. The moderating role of perceived serendipity

Serendipity is associated with something out of control such as luck, chance or accidental occurrences which trigger people to seek ways to foster and encourage such experiences (Busch, 2022). In the context of recommendation system, serendipity refers to the extent that users come across the content that match them, relevant to them but still sufficiently brings them the sense of surprise which they have never explored themselves (Chen et al., 2019; Herlocker et al., 2004; Matt et al., 2014). A content is perceived serendipitous when it meets four requirements: novelty, unexpectedness, relevance, and difficulty to discover by users (Kotkov et al., 2016). Superior to highly personalized recommendations that focus primarily on user preferences, serendipitous suggestions evoke positive feelings of surprise, thereby enhancing users' satisfaction with the system (Zhang et al., 2012).

Perceived serendipity can significantly influence how users perceive AI-based content recommendations. As without surprising suggestions, recommendations which are boring, repetitive and frustrating (Ziarani and Ravanmehr, 2021, b). Hence, more and more scholars have proposed the approach to the diversity in recommendations (Sanz-Cruzado and Castells, 2018). When AI systems focus on both relevance and serendipity, users can generate more interest and satisfaction. In terms of outcomes, perceived serendipity also influences cognitive and emotional resonance significantly. Serendipitous recommendations can help users expose themselves to various content from different fields, which in turn prompt them to explore new perspectives, think more creatively or feel emotionally uplifted. Sinha et al. (2001) defined that "A serendipitous system will challenge users to expand their tastes and hopefully provide more interesting recommendations, qualities that can help improve recommendation satisfaction".

While prior studies have examined perceived serendipity as an independent variable (Chen et al., 2025; Bao and Yang, 2022; Oh et al., 2021), the moderating role of it remains largely underexplored. Furthermore, previous research has reported contrasting findings on whether AI algorithms can consistently deliver unexpected yet relevant recommendations, and whether users benefit from such algorithmic

intentions (Kuai and Wei, 2025). This study helps address the existing research gap and responds to recent calls for investigating the impact of different levels of serendipity on marketing outcomes (Kuai and Wei, 2025) by introducing perceived serendipity as a moderator in relationship between consistency dimensions and user resonance. Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H4a. Perceived serendipity positively moderates the relationship between information consistency and emotional resonance.

H4b. Perceived serendipity positively moderates the relationship between presence consistency and emotional resonance.

H4c. Perceived serendipity positively moderates the relationship between image consistency and emotional resonance.

H4d. Perceived serendipity positively moderates the relationship between information consistency and cognitive resonance.

H4e. Perceived serendipity positively moderates the relationship between presence consistency and cognitive resonance.

H4f. Perceived serendipity positively moderates the relationship between image consistency and cognitive resonance.

1.2.8. The moderating role of platform stickiness

User stickiness has been studied widely and regarded as the extension of loyalty that makes an individual visit one store again and again for their purchase. When it comes to the time of the internet, it refers to the time a person retains on a specific platform (Li et al., 2021). Social media stickiness is built on emotional attachment and social presence (Wukich, 2022). A person with stickiness on a website will have a tendency to spend more time and more frequencies visiting this site (Xu et al., 2018). Similarly, platform stickiness in our study refers to how users stick to short video platforms with content recommendation.

A sticky platform can amplify a user's resonance by enhancing the intensity and clarity of emotional and cognitive stimuli. When users feel comfortable and immersed in a platform, they tend to experience stronger emotional resonance, such as enjoyment or identification with content, as well as cognitive resonance, including meaningful interpretation and mental alignment with the message (Shin and Biocca, 2018). Conversely, a low-stickiness environment may weaken the formation of resonance, divert user attention, and decrease message absorption. Once users stick to something, they will have positive both psychological and behavioral responses. Zhang, Li, and colleagues (2017) identified a significant relationship between customer engagement and platform stickiness. Zott et al. (2000) suggested that when customers are drawn to websites and stick to this, customers will be likely to buy more products and services which is relevant to McCloskey, (2003)'s study which also confirmed that the more time users spent on the internet, the more likely they will buy things online. Lin (2007) contended that stickiness rather than trust or website content plays a key role in affecting customer's intention to buy on online platforms.

Although most prior research treated platform stickiness as a dependent variable or behavioral outcome (Mou et al., 2024; Chakraborty and Rana, 2025; Shao et al., 2020), this study proposes that it can serve as a moderator. The rationale is that users who frequently return to or spend extended time on a platform are more receptive to content and more likely to act upon emotional and cognitive cues, such as engagement and impulse buying. A report from Market Intelligence and Consulting Institute (MIC, 2025) also recorded 70 % of consumers use social websites characterized by high stickiness, emphasizing its importance in shaping online behavior.

Due to dual influence on both resonance and behavioral responses, platform stickiness can be theorized to moderate the effects of emotional and cognitive resonance on customer engagement and impulse buying.

Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H5a. Platform stickiness positively moderates the relationship

between emotional resonance and customer engagement.

H5b. Platform stickiness positively moderates the relationship between emotional resonance and impulse buying.

H5c. Platform stickiness positively moderates the relationship between cognitive resonance and customer engagement.

H5d. Platform stickiness positively moderates the relationship between cognitive resonance and impulse buying.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data collection

We conducted a pretest with 20 respondents to make the questions readable. The translation and back translation method was used to adapt and translate all scales into Vietnamese. There were some changes in the wording of several items to ensure the questions' comprehensibility. The sampling method is a non-probability sampling approach, specifically a purposive (judgmental) sampling technique with screening-based eligibility criteria. The required sample size was determined based on the recommendations of Kline, (2016) and Hair et al. (2019) for Structural Equation Modeling, which suggest at least 10–20 cases per estimated parameter and a minimum of 200 participants for model stability. The final sample of 679 respondents from Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam therefore exceeds the recommended threshold for reliable SEM analysis. To identify eligible participants, two screening questions were used "Among the following short video platforms, which ones do you use? (TikTok For Business, 2024)?" and "When using the platforms above, do you often watch recommended videos (For You, Recommended, suggested based on your interests)?" If the participant chose "no," their questionnaire would be regarded as invalid. Before completing the survey, respondents were introduced to the research topic and given a clear explanation of "the recommendation algorithm of AI on short-video social media networks", along with illustrative examples from platforms such as TikTok, Instagram Reels, YouTube Shorts, Facebook to aid comprehension. On average, the survey took 15–20 min to complete. Every participant was assured that all responses and personal data would remain confidential. We used SMARTPLS 4 software to conduct exploratory factor analysis. Of the 679 initial responses, 46 were excluded due to respondents not watching recommended content, leaving 633 valid responses for analysis. Among the respondents, 287 were male (45 %) and 346 were female (55 %). Most participants (69.5 %) were aged between 18 and 24, while the smallest group (0.9 %) fell between 35 and 44 years. Regarding education background, 58.3 % were university students, followed by high school students (12.3 %), secondary school students (10.7 %), postgraduates (10.1 %), and bachelor's degree holders (8.5 %). Finally, in terms of income, 78.8 % reported earning under 10 million VND, followed by 13.4 % earning between 10 and 20 million VND per month, 4.1 % earning from 51 to 60 million VND per month, 2.5 % earning from 21 to 30 million VND, and lastly, 1.1 % earning from 41 to 50 million VND (see Table 1). Gen Z is the key user group of short-videos and purchasing behavior is enabled on this platform. Many industry reports and studies show that short-form videos (TikTok/Reels/Shorts) are a strong product discovery and interaction channel among Gen Z. These platforms create many discovery => engagement => purchase pathways, especially for low value/impulse transactions. Targeting Gen Z helps research focus on the population of interest (those directly affected by AI-recommendation in the short-video environment) (TikTok for Busch, 2022). Studies on youth behavior show that: teenagers are an influential consumer group and have impulsive behavior in e-commerce, live-stream, short-video, especially for low-value products; they are both consumers and sources of influence on purchasing decisions (with or without parental approval) (Zhang, 2024b; Smith and Johnson, 2023; Yarborough and Miller, 2024). Participants under 18 were included to reflect real-world market

participation, though ethical considerations and parental influence are acknowledged as study limitations (see Table 2).

2.2. Measures

All items were adapted from the literature to reflect the following constructs: information consistency, presence consistency, image consistency; four dimensions of emotional resonances - congruence, entertainment, inspiration and escapism; and three dimensions of cognitive resonance - information acquisition, source credibility, and knowledge externalization. Additionally, the model incorporates platform stickiness, perceived serendipity, impulse buying and customer engagement, which comprises five aspects: learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy, co-developing. All items were refined to ensure contextual appropriateness. Following the modifications, they were translated from English to Vietnamese to ensure participants' comprehension (Harkness et al., 2004). Responses were measured on a seven-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

Information consistency was assessed using four items from Brodie et al. (2013). Items for presence consistency and image consistency were drawn from Cheung et al. (2012). Emotional resonance was measured with thirteen items sourced from Wang et al. (2023). Cognitive resonance, comprising information acquisition, source credibility were derived from Wang et al. (2023) using five items, while knowledge externalization was adapted from Schulze and Hoegl (2006) with three items. Platform stickiness was measured by six items adapted from Sun et al., (2023), Ashfaq et al. (2025), Zhang et al. (2017), Wen and Chu (2022), Zhu et al. (2018). Perceived serendipity was captured using four items from Zhao and Wagner (2022), Lu and Cheng (2020). Impulse buying was measured via three items from Beatty and Ferrell (1998). Customer engagement consists of five dimensions, each assessed using three items based on Brodie et al. (2013). Among these variables, emotional resonance, cognitive resonance and customer engagement are second-order constructs using the repeated indicator approach proposed by (Chin et al., 2003). In this approach, the second-order constructs are directly measured using all observed indicators of first-ordered dimensions.

2.3. Data analysis

We use the partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS4 software (Becker et al., 2023) to test the theoretical model (see Fig. 1) and proposed hypotheses. PLS-SEM allows research findings to strike a balance between explanation and prediction (Lim et al., 2023). One of its key advantages is that it does not impose strict distributional requirements, allowing researchers to analyze complex models that include multiple constructs, indicator variables, and interrelated paths (Hair et al., 2019). Additionally, this technique is well-suited for an intricate research model with moderating effects and reflective-formative higher-order constructs (Becker et al., 2022a; Cheah et al., 2023). This technique also facilitates the simultaneous estimation of multiple independent variables and the examination of composite-based path relationships (Hair et al., 2022). Considering these outweighs, SMARTPLS4 was employed to conduct the model assessment (see Fig. 1).

3. Results

3.1. Common method bias (CMB)

This paper utilizes the single-source data collection method - questionnaire surveys, which may result in variable covariance and create challenges in data analysis (Campbell and Fiske, 1959; MacKenzie and Podsakoff, 2012). Thus, we examine both procedural and statistical remedies to explore whether there is the influence of CMB or not. While procedural controls are applied before data gathering (ex ante),

Table 1
Previous studies and contribution of this research into the current domain.

Authors	Antecedent	Outcomes	Mediator/Moderator	Theory	Country/ Territory	Key findings
Hsieh (2023)	Information consistency, Image consistency	Purchase intention, eWOM intention	Cognitive identification, Affective identification	Cue consistency theory, Social identity theory, SOR theory	A territory with an Eastern cultural background (Taiwan)	Influencers' consistent cues enhance followers' cognitive and affective identification, which in turn drive purchase and eWOM intentions. The type of influencer moderates these relationships: cognitive identification has a stronger impact on purchase intention for review-type influencers, whereas affective identification more strongly influences behavioral intentions for lifestyle-type influencers.
Wang et al. (2023)	Online travel information quality (Value-added, Relevance, Timeliness, Completeness, Interestingness, Design, Amount of information)	Conative Image	Cognitive Resonance (Information acquisition, Source credibility), Emotional Resonance (Entertainment, Inspiration, Escapism, Self-congruence)	Resonance theory	China	Four dimensions of online travel information quality (value-added, relevancy, completeness, and design) enhance cognitive resonance, while three dimensions (interestingness, design, and amount of information) foster emotional resonance. Both cognitive and emotional resonance positively influence the conative travel intentions.
Zhang and Wang (2025)	Information quality, Perceived similarity, Decision support tool, Recommendation signal, Community atmosphere	Psychological engagement, Behavioral engagement	Cognitive resonance, Emotional resonance	Resonance theory, SOR theory	China	Information quality, perceived similarity, decision support tool, recommendation signal, and community atmosphere influence cognitive and emotional resonance, which sequentially drive psychological and behavioral engagement. Community atmosphere moderates the above relationships.
Lazaris et al. (2022)	Additive Omnichannel Atmospheric Cues (Physical store channel cues, Mobile channel cues, IoT, Social media channel)	Purchase intention	Cognitive Response (Perceived store environment), Affective Response (Pleasure, Arousal, Dominance)	SOR theory	Greece	Consumers' affective and cognitive states mediate purchase intention when exposed to additive omnichannel stimuli. Additionally, integrating IoT and social media channels significantly enhances pleasure and arousal, while dominance remains unchanged.
Rajat et al. (2024)	Website credibility	Online Impulse Buying	Need for touch, Visual appeal, Hedonic Shopping Motivation	Cognitive Appraisal Theory	Malaysia	Website credibility significantly influences hedonic shopping motivation, visual appeal and need for touch, but does not directly affect impulse buying. While visual appeal and need for touch alone do not result in impulse purchases, hedonic shopping motivation is the strongest and most consistent predictor of online impulse buying.
Cheng et al. (2020)	Cognitive resonance (information acquisition, source credibility, video quality), Emotional resonance (Entertainment, inspiration, escapism, self-congruence)	Travel intention	Customer engagement behaviors (Word-of-mouth)	Theory of resonance	Not given	Source credibility is the strongest cognitive predictor of WOM intention, while its effect on travel intention is negative. Emotional resonance factors, particularly inspiration and escapism exert a stronger impact on WOM than cognitive ones.
Li et al. (2021)	Technical factors (synchronicity, vicarious expression) and social factors (interaction, identification)	Emotional attachment to streamers and Platform attachment	User stickiness	Attachment theory	China	Both technical and social factors significantly enhance emotional and platform attachment in live shopping environments. Emotional attachment to

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Authors	Antecedent	Outcomes	Mediator/Moderator	Theory	Country/Territory	Key findings
Huang et al. (2024)	Number of Likes, Number of Comments, Product attraction, Media attraction	Impulse buying	Product type, Controls (Time Span, Video length, Follow number, Price)	Social proof theory	China	streamer arises through real-time communication and social interaction, while technical features improve the shopping experience, fostering platform attachment. The number of likes and comments positively affects impulse buying behavior on short-video platforms. Product attraction shows a negative relationship with impulse buying, while media attraction has a positive influence.
Zhang et al. (2024)	Anchor characteristics, Time pressure, Livestream activity	Impulse buying	Consumer vulnerability, Product type	SOR theory	China	Anchors' credibility, professionalism, and attractiveness significantly increase consumers' impulse buying behavior. Higher live stream activity promotes impulse consumption by creating social influence and herd effects. Time-limited offer and short product demonstrations increase perceived urgency, leading consumers to make quick, less rational purchases. Consumer vulnerability acts as mediators.
Current study	Information consistency, image consistency, presence consistency	Impulse buying, Customer engagement (learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy, co-developing)	Cognitive resonance (Information acquisition, source credibility, knowledge externalization), Emotional resonance (Congruence, Entertainment, Inspiration, Escapism)	Cue consistency, Resonance theory, SOR theory	Vietnam	Presence consistency leads to emotional resonance while information and image consistency influence cognitive resonance. Additionally, cognitive resonance results in impulse buying, whereas the relationship between emotional resonance and customer engagement is moderated by platform stickiness.

Table 2 Demographic characteristics.

Variable	Responses	Total number	Percentage %
Gender	Toal	633	
	Male	287	45
Age	Female	346	55
	Total	633	
	Under 18 years old	153	24.2
	From 18 to 24 years old	440	69.5
	From 25 to 34 years old	34	5.4
	From 35 to 44 years old	6	0.9
Education	Over 45 years old	0	0
	Total	633	
	Secondary School	68	10.7
	High School	78	12.3
	Bachelor's Degree	54	8.5
Income	University	369	58.3
	Postgraduate degree	64	10.1
	Total	633	
	Under 10 million VND/month	499	78.8
	From 10 to 20 million VND/month	85	13.4
	From 21 to 30 million VND/month	16	2.5
	From 31 to 40 million VND/month	0	0
From 41 to 50 million VND/month	7	1.1	
From 51 to 60 million VND/month	26	4.1	
Over 60 million VND/month	0	0	

statistical techniques are applied afterward (ex post). Procedural controls aim to prevent or limit common method bias by designing questionnaires carefully. For example, enhancing response accuracy can be

achieved by giving respondents clear instructions, clarifying that there are no right or wrong answers and assuring anonymity. To maintain participant interest, it is necessary to keep surveys brief and free from repetitive questions. Finally, including both positively and negatively worded items and creating psychological separation between independent and dependent variables can reduce bias. In this study, procedural remedies include translating the questionnaire into Vietnamese and providing detailed explanations of specific terms, which helps ensure item clarity, reduce misunderstandings, and make participants more comfortable (MacKenzie and Podsakoff, 2012). Second, two tests are conducted: the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) in the inner model (Kock, 2015) and Harman's single-factor test (Fuller et al., 2016). Results show that all VIF values lie between 1.00 and 2.499, which is well below the accepted limit of 3.33 (Hair et al., 2021). Also, the highest variance explained by a single factor is 43.828 %, which is smaller than 50 %. Therefore, the findings suggest that CMB is not a concern in this study.

3.2. Measurement model

The findings (Table 3) indicate that all item outer loadings are higher than the suggested threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021), confirming acceptable indicator reliability. Moreover, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct surpasses the 0.5 level, reflecting sufficient convergent validity and positive inter-variable associations (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2016; Hair et al., 2021). In addition, Composite Reliability (CR) values exceed the recommended cutoff of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021). Regarding internal consistency, Cronbach's Alpha values in this study range from 0.728 to 0.922 for most constructs, exceeding the

Fig. 1. Research model (Authors' Own Work).

commonly accepted threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021), which supports the reliability of the measurement scales.

To assess discriminant validity, this study employed both the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) (see Table 4) and the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Henseler et al., 2015b) (see Table 5). HTMT values are below the commonly recommended threshold of 0.85, indicating that discriminant validity is not critically violated. Moreover, the Fornell-Larcker criterion is satisfied, as the square root of each construct's AVE is greater than its correlations with other constructs (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Based on this combination of results, the model's discriminant validity is considered acceptable, and the constructs are retained for further analysis. The results reveal that each latent construct such as consistency, resonance, customer engagement, and impulse buying captures a distinct conceptual domain. This means the measurements used for each construct are separable, reducing the risk of overlapping each other and reinforcing the proposed model (see Table 6).

3.3. Structural model

After running bootstrapping, we find that the R² values are between 0.492 and 0.613, which signifies a moderate level of regression model performance. The Normal Fit Index (NFI) of the estimated model is 0.781, which exceeds the acceptable threshold of 0.7, while the SRMR value is 0.071 (see Table 6), remaining below the cut-off value of 0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Together, these fit indices suggest that measurement model demonstrates an overall fit and provides a solid foundation for testing the hypothesized structural relationships. Table 7 presents the latent variable correlations. In addition, all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values in the Outer Model are below 5.0, suggesting that collinearity is not a significant concern (Hair et al., 2019). The initial phase of the inner model analysis displays the significance levels of the hypothesized paths. The results in Table 8 show that several hypotheses were supported. Notably, Perceived Serendipity and Emotional Resonance holds the strongest association (b = 0.491), followed by Perceived Serendipity and Cognitive Resonance (b = 0.351). Additionally, Image Consistency showed a positive impact on Cognitive Resonance (b = 0.166). Conversely, a number of hypotheses failed to reach statistical significance, as their p-value exceeds the 0.05 threshold (0.231, 0.121, 0.090, and 0.058), suggesting that these relationships were not supported by the data in this study (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2016).

3.4. Analyses of moderation

The model (see Fig. 1) includes interaction variables to assess how two factors moderate effects. First, Perceived Serendipity moderates

how Information Consistency, Presence Consistency and Image Consistency impacts Cognitive Resonance (Information Acquisition, Source Credibility and Knowledge Externalization). Second, Platform Stickiness moderates how Emotional Resonance (Congruence, Entertainment, Inspiration, Escapism) influences both Impulse buying and Customer Engagement (Learning, Sharing, Socializing, Advocacy, Co-developing).

None of the interaction effects involving Perceived Serendipity were statistically significant, indicating that Perceived Serendipity does not significantly moderate the relationships between Information Consistency, Presence Consistency, or Image Consistency and Cognitive Resonance (PE x IC -> CR, $\beta = -0,049$, $p = 0,479$; PE x IM -> CR, $\beta = 0,060$, $p = 0,338$; PE x PC -> CR, $\beta = -0,046$, $p = 0,446$).

With respect to Platform Stickiness, it moderates the relationship between Emotional Resonance and Impulse buying (PS x ER -> IP, $\beta = 0,101$, $p < 0,05$), suggesting that when users find the platform sticky or engaging, emotional resonance more strongly boosts their Impulse purchase. However, no significant moderating effect was found of Platform Stickiness on the relationship between Emotional Resonance and Customer Engagement (PS x ER -> CE, $\beta = 0,059$, $p = 0,375$).

In sum, among the moderation hypotheses, only PS x ER -> IP was supported, while PE x IC -> CR, PE x IM -> CR, PE x PC -> CR, PS x ER -> CE showed either non-significant or borderline results.

4. Discussion

This study empirically tests the influence of AI-based content recommendation characterized by information consistency, presence consistency and image consistency on customer engagement and impulse buying behavior, with the focus on emotional resonance and cognitive resonance. Additionally, this study examines the moderating role of perceived serendipity and platform stickiness in two pathways: the effect of AI-based content recommendation on emotional resonance, and the effect of cognitive resonance on impulse purchase.

Although we hypothesized that all three dimensions of AI-based content recommendation consistency would positively influence emotional resonance, the result shows that only presence consistency plays a meaningful role. This pattern can be understood via the concept of brand familiarity (Kent and Allen, 1994; Dahln and Lange, 2004), which posits that familiarity of consumers towards brands will help consumers process them with less effort, and these brands are preferred. Studies from Lee and Labroo (2004); Labroo and Lee (2006); Novemsky et al. (2007) also stated that brands that are familiar to consumers can have more effect on cognition and emotion; they can be recognized and identified more easily. Thus, it is possible to conclude presence consistency influences emotional resonance. In contrast, the other two types of consistency - information and image consistency did not show a significant effect on emotional resonance. Although these consistencies may

Table 3
The reliability and convergent validity.

Constructs	FL	CA	CR	AVE
Information Consistency (Second Order)		0.728	0.831	0.554
IC1	0.760			
IC2	0.817			
IC3	0.741			
IC4	0.750			
Presence Consistency (Second Order)		0.716	0.838	0.721
PC1	0.818			
PC2	0.879			
Image Consistency (Second Order)		0.796	0.831	0.622
IM1	0.768			
IM2	0.803			
IM3	0.794			
Emotional Resonance (Second Order)		0.878	0.916	0.733
Congruence (First Order)	0.886	0.801	0.870	0.764
ER1	0.792			
ER2	0.789			
ER3	0.821			
ER4	0.762			
Entertainment (First Order)	0.847	0.763	0.863	0.678
ER5	0.828			
ER6	0.805			
ER7	0.838			
Inspiration (First Order)	0.854	0.797	0.869	0.768
ER8	0.876			
ER9	0.876			
Escapism (First Order)	0.837	0.843	0.895	0.680
ER10	0.840			
ER11	0.821			
ER12	0.816			
ER13	0.823			
Cognitive Resonance (Second Order)		0.765	0.865	0.681
Information Acquisition (First Order)	0.774	0.707	0.872	0.733
CR1	0.871			
CR2	0.888			
Source Credibility (First Order)	0.840	0.762	0.863	0.677
CR3	0.828			
CR4	0.804			
CR5	0.837			
Knowledge Externalization (First Order)	0.859	0.786	0.875	0.701
CR6	0.796			
CR7	0.842			
CR8	0.872			
Platform Stickiness (Second Order)		0.853	0.891	0.576
PS1	0.734			
PS2	0.755			
PS3	0.785			
PS4	0.769			
PS5	0.798			
PS6	0.710			
Perceived Serendipity (Second Order)		0.851	0.900	0.692
PE1	0.826			
PE2	0.852			
PE3	0.809			
PE4	0.840			
Impulse Buying (Second Order)		0.837	0.902	0.755
IP1	0.851			
IP2	0.893			
IP3	0.861			
Customer Engagement (Second Order)		0.922	0.942	0.764
Learning (First Order)	0.849	0.822	0.894	0.737
CE1	0.845			
CE2	0.868			
CE3	0.862			
Sharing (First Order)	0.882	0.825	0.896	0.741
CE4	0.855			
CE5	0.870			
CE6	0.857			
Socializing (First Order)	0.901	0.819	0.892	0.734
CE7	0.844			
CE8	0.857			
CE9	0.868			
Advocacy (First Order)	0.875	0.814	0.890	0.729
CE10	0.838			
CE11	0.863			

Table 3 (continued)

Constructs	FL	CA	CR	AVE
CE12	0.859			
Co-developing (First Order)	0.861	0.863	0.916	0.784
CE13	0.886			
CE14	0.891			
CE15	0.880			

Abbreviations: AVE: Average variance extracted; CA: Cronbach's alpha; CR: Composite reliability; FL: factor loading.

enhance message clarity and visual coherence, they might not be sufficient to stimulate the curiosity and desire required to generate (Kang et al., 2020), especially in short video platforms where attention spans are shorter. In the context of cognitive resonance, only information consistency and image consistency have a positive impact on cognitive resonance. This result is in accordance with Hsieh (2023), who found that information and image consistency of influencers in social networking sites enhance social identification, both cognitively and affectively, which subsequently boosts behavioral intention. Conversely, this pattern was not observed for presence consistency. Cognitive resonance stems from audience's beliefs and understanding (Giorgi, 2017) and can be achieved when individuals interpret information in a way that matches their expectation (Shang et al., 2017). While presence consistency may enhance familiarity through repeated exposure to the same brands, creators, or content, it may lack the informational depth or novelty to provoke their cognition.

The study also reveals the significant positive impact of cognitive resonance and on impulse buying, indicating that when users cognitively align with content - perceiving it as credible, relevant, or familiar, they are more likely to make unplanned purchases. Although prior studies have not directly examined this linkage, Wu and Lai (2022) argued that cognitive resonance - arising from content usefulness, novelty, and credibility - plays a key role in fostering psychological and behavioral engagement in short video environments. This finding can be interpreted within the framework of SOR, where cognitive resonance functions as an internal state that mediates between content stimuli and behavioral responses. In the context of short videos, the highly personalized and repetitive nature of AI-based content may facilitate knowledge internalization, thus increasing user's readiness to act on impulse. Moreover, this study aimed to examine the relationship between emotional resonance and impulse buying in the context of short videos, responding to the call for further research made by (Chen and Yao, 2018; Parboteeah et al., 2009; Xiang et al., 2016). However, this result did not support the relationship between emotional resonance and impulse buying. This contradicts prior research such as (Akram et al., 2018; Compen et al., 2021), which highlighted the critical role of emotional responses such as pleasure or arousal in triggering impulsive purchases, particularly when social influence is present. One possible reason for this discrepancy is the fleeting nature of emotional experiences in short video environments. Unlike long-form content, short videos may not allow enough time for emotional resonance to develop deeply enough to influence behavior. In contrast, cognitive resonance may provide quicker and more actionable cues in such fast-paced digital contexts thanks to its relevance, credibility and information richness.

Emotional and cognitive resonance appear to shape customer engagement which is consistent with a study from Zhang and Wang (2025), demonstrating that emotional resonance in the context of traveling videos can lead to psychological engagement and behavioral engagement, including buying behavior. Regarding cognitive resonance, Yu (2021) found that cognitive resonance may result in online engagement by increasing perceived personal involvement. However, in this research, the relationship between cognitive resonance and customer engagement was not supported, possibly because engagement on short video platforms are often triggered more by more stunning elements rather than cognitive alignment.

Table 4
Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT).

	CE	CR	ER	IC	IM	IP	PC	PE	PS
CE									
CR	0,830								
ER	0,798	0,773							
IC	0,588	0,777	0,672						
IM	0,596	0,762	0,657	0,782					
IP	0,805	0,755	0,693	0,697	0,649				
PC	0,604	0,753	0,726	0,733	0,798	0,600			
PE	0,795	0,772	0,808	0,730	0,708	0,798	0,727		
PS	0,791	0,845	0,832	0,717	0,728	0,841	0,683	0,733	

Note: CE: Customer Engagement, CR: Cognitive Resonance; ER: Emotional Resonance; IC: Information Consistency; IM: Image Consistency; IP: Impulse buying; PC: Presence Consistency; PE: Perceived Serendipity; PS: Platform Stickiness.

Table 5
Fornell - larcker criterion.

	CE	CR	ER	IC	IM	IP	PC	PE	PS
CE	0,874								
CR	0,697	0,825							
ER	0,718	0,798	0,856						
IC	0,481	0,580	0,537	0,744					
IM	0,478	0,556	0,514	0,698	0,789				
IP	0,707	0,604	0,595	0,545	0,495	0,869			
PC	0,460	0,520	0,538	0,624	0,591	0,431	0,849		
PE	0,705	0,623	0,698	0,572	0,545	0,674	0,528	0,832	
PS	0,702	0,681	0,719	0,566	0,560	0,712	0,498	0,794	0,759

Note: CE: Customer Engagement, CR: Cognitive Resonance; ER: Emotional Resonance; IC: Information Consistency; IM: Image Consistency; IP: Impulse buying; PC: Presence Consistency; PE: Perceived Serendipity; PS: Platform Stickiness.

Table 6
Model_Fit-fit summary.

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.053	0.079
d_ULS	1.661	3.743
d_G	0.746	0.910
Chi-square	2867,298	3105,024
NFI	0,797	0,781

Furthermore, this study also investigates the moderating role of perceived serendipity and platform stickiness. However, only platform stickiness seems to moderate the relationship emotional resonance and customer engagement. This suggests that the stickier a platform is, the more effectively emotional resonance translates into active engagement. This study is the first to examine this moderating relationship, however, there are previous ones which examined how platform stickiness influences emotional resonance as well as how platform stickiness affects customer engagement. This finding echoes (Shin and Biocca, 2018) who found that users are more likely to develop emotional resonance when they feel at ease and fully engaged with a platform. Zhang et al. (2017) also confirmed there is a notable connection between how engaged customers are and their tendency to remain on a platform. Therefore, it is possible to conclude platform stickiness’s moderating role. On the

Table 7
Latent variable correlations.

	CE	CR	ER	IC	IM	IP	PC	PE	PS
CE	1.000	0.697	0.718	0.481	0.478	0.707	0.460	0.705	0.702
CR	0.697	1.000	0.798	0.580	0.556	0.604	0.520	0.623	0.681
ER	0.718	0.798	1.000	0.537	0.514	0.595	0.538	0.698	0.719
IC	0.481	0.580	0.537	1.000	0.698	0.545	0.624	0.572	0.566
IM	0.478	0.556	0.514	0.698	1.000	0.495	0.591	0.545	0.560
IP	0.707	0.604	0.595	0.545	0.495	1.000	0.431	0.674	0.712
PC	0.460	0.520	0.538	0.624	0.591	0.431	1.000	0.528	0.498
PE	0.705	0.623	0.698	0.572	0.545	0.674	0.528	1.000	0.794
PS	0.702	0.681	0.719	0.566	0.560	0.712	0.498	0.794	1.000

other hand, perceived serendipity was not proved to moderate any relationships. Perceived serendipity emphasizes whether the user feels pleasantly surprised when encountering a relevant recommendation, which implies that the item should not only match the user’s interests but also be unexpected (Chen et al., 2019). Sinha et al. (2001) found that serendipity can enhance recommendation systems and make them more interesting to audiences, however, the lack of significance in this study may be explained by the discovery-oriented nature of short video platforms, where unexpected yet relevant content is already common. As a result, the additional effect of perceived serendipity on engagement or purchase behavior may not be counted.

Finally, this study goes beyond prior studies in the same area as it does not only learn the dependent relationship but also the moderating role of platform stickiness and perceived serendipity. This is because how people perceive AI-based content recommendation relevant to them but at the same time brings them the sense of surprise and their stickiness to short video platforms can bring them engagement and eventually impulse buying behavior. These results are somewhat similar to other studies like (Nguyen et al., 2024) which studies AI-based content recommendation on customer engagement.

Table 8
Path coefficients-mean, p values.

Hypothesis	Original Sample	P values	Decision
CR - > CE = H4a	0,221	0,000	Accepted
CR - > IP = H3b	0,182	0,009	Accepted
ER - > CE = H4b	0,282	0,000	Accepted
ER - > IP = H3a	0,086	0,231	Rejected
IC - > CR = H2a	0,187	0,002	Accepted
IC - > ER = H1a	0,080	0,121	Rejected
IM - > CR = H2c	0,166	0,006	Accepted
IM - > ER = H1c	0,095	0,058	Rejected
PC - > CR = H2b	0,092	0,090	Rejected
PC - > ER = H1b	0,127	0,018	Accepted
PE - > CR	0,351	0,000	Accepted
PE - > ER	0,491	0,000	Accepted
PE x IC - > CR = H6d	-0,049	0,479	Rejected
PE x IC - > ER = H6b	-0,082	0,204	Rejected
PE x IM - > CR = H6f	0,060	0,338	Rejected
PE x IM - > ER = H6a	0,103	0,052	Rejected
PE x PC - > CR = H6e	-0,046	0,446	Rejected
PE x PC - > ER = H6c	-0,080	0,113	Rejected
PS - > CE	0,329	0,000	Accepted
PS - > IP	0,553	0,000	Accepted
PS x CR - > CE = H5c	-0,093	0,153	Rejected
PS x CR - > IP = H5d	-0,081	0,118	Rejected
PS x ER - > CE = H5b	0,059	0,375	Rejected
PS x ER - > IP = H5a	0,101	0,045	Accepted

5. Implications

5.1. Theoretical implications

Our study contributes to the theoretical understanding of AI-driven recommendation by using cue consistency theory and resonance theory within the context of short video platforms. First, this study extends cue consistency theory beyond traditional human-generated cues. While prior research learned about corroborating cues across sources on consumer quality perception (Akdeniz et al., 2012) or influencer-driven messaging on social media (Hsieh, 2023). We conceptualize information consistency, image consistency and presence consistency as machine-generated cues and examine how they influence user responses. Second, we expand the application of resonance theory, which was previously used in tourism and sociological contexts (Wang et al., 2023), by applying it to short-form algorithm content. We show that consistent cues can trigger emotional and cognitive resonance, leading to impulse buying and customer engagement - reflecting a dual pathway of media impact. Next, we enrich the concept of customer engagement by adopting a five-dimensional structure: learning, sharing, socializing, advocacy, and co-developing, which helps to thoroughly assess the engaging level of viewers after watching recommendations on short-video platforms. Fourth, our study refines cognitive resonance by incorporating knowledge externalization, aligned with knowledge creation theory (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995), emphasizing that users not only acquire information but also reshape and share it. Finally, by introducing platform stickiness and perceived serendipity as moderators, we highlight how experiential factors shape how users absorb and act upon AI-driven content.

5.2. Practical implications

First of all, the study highlights the value of presence consistency - the repeated appearance of specific brands, creators, or themes in recommended videos in strengthening emotional resonance. When users encounter familiar faces or messages over time, they are more likely to feel connected and positively disposed toward the brand. It is recommended that platform developers design AI algorithms that balance novelty with familiarity - ensuring that video topics and themes remain diverse but not scattered, and still aligned with audience taste. For marketers, they should have a strategic plan not only for their own short-

video accounts but also for satellite channels such as KOL/KOC reviews, ensuring that content across platforms consistently reflects the brand's identity and message. Influencers can also benefit by maintaining a consistent appearance, theme, or set of topics to foster recognition and emotional attachment. Secondly, information consistency and image consistency were proved to boost cognitive resonance. It is advisable that content creators should maintain their theme, tone, or visual style, message aligned across videos to boost visibility and trust. If a creator frequently switches between unrelated topics or presentation styles, it can confuse new viewers and weaken their perception of credibility. Digital advertisers should focus on building a stable brand identity by using familiar visual elements, messaging, and aesthetics that viewers can easily recognize and trust. For example, Red Bull maintains a distinctive content style and visual identity focused on extreme sports. Their short videos consistently use the same color tones, logo, and the message "Red Bull gives you wings" (Kantar, 2024). Maintaining a consistent brand image and message helps Red Bull strengthen credibility and increase audience trust. Third, while emotional content can drive attention and interest, the study reveals that cognitive resonance - built through credible information and useful knowledge can also lead to impulse buying. This suggests that marketers should not rely solely on emotions to drive conversions. Performance-driven brands should prioritize convey helpful, credible information such as reviewers, usage guides, or tutorials, which encourage viewers to process and share information more actively. Consumers today prefer to view products before making a purchase Think with Google (2025). As a result, they engage with videos showcasing influencers' shopping experiences or providing detailed information about products, which helps build their trust. E-commerce sellers can leverage this effect by attaching products directly to short videos (e.g., TikTok Shop), enabling audiences to purchase immediately after watching. Accounts that provide reliable, informative content are more likely to spark cognitive resonance and generate sales. Therefore, they can totally generate revenue if their account creates videos helpful in providing credible information and triggering cognitive resonance. Finally, the study highlights the role of platform stickiness in strengthening relationship between emotional resonance and customer engagement. The longer users stay on a platform, the more opportunities there are for emotional connections to translate into active engagement. Platform managers therefore should invest in features like personalized recommendation, content filters, or interactive tools that make users more likely to stay and return.

6. Limitation and future research

Future studies should consider addressing several limitations identified in the current research. First, while this study was conducted in Vietnam, future research should explore broader geographical regions to enhance the generalizability of findings and minimize the constraints posed by localized data collection. Second, approximately one-fourth of respondents were under 18 years old, whose media consumption patterns and cognitive maturity differ from adults. We intentionally included this group because teenagers are a substantial portion of short-video users and engage in frequent low-value, in-app purchases; however, their decision-making processes may also differ due to parental influence and developmental factors. Therefore, we acknowledge this as a limitation and recommend that future research either (a) restrict the sample to over 18 for direct comparability, or (b) perform multi-group analyses to test differences between under-18 and adult cohorts. Third, some hypothesized relationships in this study were not supported, suggesting that the underlying mechanism might be more complex than initially expected. For example, the insignificant link between image, information consistency and emotional resonance may indicate that emotional resonance is a multifaceted construct influenced by factors beyond the current model's scope, suggesting that future studies should further explore. Also, the unsupported link between emotional resonance and impulse buying should be revisited in the context of longer-

form video platforms such as Youtube, where slower-paced content may allow emotional resonance to develop more fully and translate into impulse behavioral outcomes. It is also advisable for future authors to use alternative research methods such as focus groups, in-depth interview, observation to offer richer insights into individuals' perceptions or mitigate potential biases arising from self-reported data. Finally, future studies could also expand the model by further investigating long-term outcomes such as customer loyalty, brand advocacy, and positive word-of-mouth to provide a more holistic understanding of how emotional and cognitive resonance contribute to sustained consumer-brand relationships.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thuy Do Xuan Nguyen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Khoi Minh Nguyen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Ethical compliance

The research process involving human participants followed the ethical standards of the institutional and national research committees of the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments, as well as related ethical standards.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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